

THE PERCEIVED FINANCIAL WELL-BEING OF LOCAL WORKFORCE IN PANGLAO, BOHOL AMIDST BUSINESS GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid expansion of business establishments driven largely by tourism in Panglao, Bohol, understanding the financial well-being of the local workforce becomes vital. This study examined the perceived financial well-being of the local workforce in Panglao, Bohol. Specifically, it assessed and compared the financial well-being of college and non-college graduates in terms of daily financial control, ability to absorb financial shocks, tracking and achieving financial goals, and financial freedom. The researchers employed a descriptive-comparative research design, collecting data from 388 local workers equally divided between college and non-college graduates across major economic sectors, which were analyzed using frequency counts, weighted mean, t-test, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The study reveals that the local workforce generally experienced a moderate to high extent of perceived financial well-being, suggesting that business growth has positively influenced financial conditions. However, college graduates consistently perceive a higher extent of financial well-being across all dimensions compared to non-college graduates. Significant differences in perceived financial well-being were also observed when respondents were grouped according to selected demographic variables. The findings underscore the importance of educational attainment in enhancing financial well-being and highlight the need for inclusive policies,

skills development, and financial literacy initiatives to ensure that economic growth benefits all segments of the local workforce.

Keywords: *Financial well-being, local workforce, college graduates, non-college graduates, daily financial control, financial resilience, financial goal achievement, financial freedom, tourism-driven economy, educational attainment, demographic differences, financial literacy*

INTRODUCTION

Panglao, Bohol, has undergone significant economic growth in recent years, mainly driven by the tourism boom and the rise of business establishments. According to the Panglao Tourism Office Facts and Figures Presentation (2018), cited by Chavez (2018) in her Rappler report “Panglao: Riding the tourism cash cow,” tourist arrivals began increasing significantly in 2014 alongside the growth of hotels and resort chains. By April 2018, Panglao had 2,196 registered businesses and 3,386 accommodation facilities, with tourism contributing 80% of the municipality’s revenue. As of 2025, Skyscanner ranks Panglao eighth among top travel destinations and one of the top 10 trending destinations for 2025.

The Philippine News Agency (2025) reports that flight searches for Panglao rose by 77% in early 2024, signaling rising interest. Major infrastructure investments are underway, supported by data from the Tourism Infrastructure and Enterprise Zone Authority (TIEZA) in 2024, which highlights Panglao’s strong potential for tourism and business. Although this expansion brings income and livelihood opportunities, its benefits to residents remain uneven and unclear, with educational attainment seen as a key factor in who benefits most.

Educational attainment has long been recognized as a critical determinant of socio-economic mobility and individual economic success. According to Oreopoulos and Petronijevic (2013), higher levels of education generally lead to better employment opportunities, higher earnings, and greater economic security, but the benefits are not always uniformly distributed across different communities or economic sectors.

In Panglao, Bohol, where business growth is rapidly reshaping the local economy, the role of educational attainment becomes even more significant. College graduates may be better positioned to access higher-skilled and higher-paying jobs emerging from the tourism and service industries, while non-graduates might find themselves limited to lower-wage, less stable employment.

This study is motivated by the need to understand the extent of financial well-being among the college and non-college local workforce during the surge in business activity in Panglao. While many factors influence financial well-being, there is a limited amount of research on the topic. This study addresses that gap by taking a broader approach, examining whether perceived financial well-being differs between the two educational groups across various demographic factors, such as age, marital status, monthly income,

number of dependents, and job position, in order to provide deeper insights into perceived financial well-being.

Research Questions

This study sought to examine the financial well-being of the college and non-college local workforce in Panglao, Bohol.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 marital status;
 - 1.3 monthly income;
 - 1.4 number of dependents; and
 - 1.5 job position?
2. To what extent do the respondents employ the elements of financial well-being in terms of:
 - 2.1. daily financial control;
 - 2.2 ability to absorb financial shocks;
 - 2.3 tracking and achieving financial goals; and
 - 2.4 financial freedom?
3. What is the extent of financial well-being among the college and non-college local workforce?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perceived financial well-being of the respondents when grouped according to demographic profile?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design and comparative research design in order to achieve the purpose of this study, which was to determine the difference in financial well-being of the local workforce from college and non-college graduates. Descriptive research was designed to describe one or more variables (Aggarwal & Ranganathan, 2018). In this study, the researchers described two variables, which were the local workforce and financial well-being.

The researchers used the comparative research design to determine the difference in financial well-being between two groups, which were the college graduates and non-college graduates of the local workforce. The comparison considered key variables such as age, marital status, monthly income, number of dependents, and job position to assess how these factors might have influenced financial well-being across the two groups. According to Richardson (2018), comparative research design essentially compared two groups in an attempt to draw a conclusion about them.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Panglao, Bohol, a tourism-driven municipality experiencing rapid business expansion. Panglao's growing hospitality and service sectors have significantly influenced local employment opportunities, making it an appropriate setting for examining financial well-being. This environment enabled the assessment and comparison of perceived financial well-being across demographic groups of the local workforce amid sustained business growth.

Research Participants

The study involved 388 local workers from Panglao, Bohol. The sample size was determined using Slovin's formula based on a workforce population of 11,659 reported by the Public Employment Service Office–Panglao. A stratified purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure equal representation of college graduates ($n = 194$) and non-college graduates ($n = 194$). Participants were drawn from Panglao's major economic sectors—tourism, hospitality, retail and trade, and transportation and real estate—with 97 respondents selected from each sector. Eligible participants were at least 18 years old, had resided in Panglao for a minimum of three years, and had been employed since 2018 to ensure exposure to recent business expansion. Only individuals willing to participate and meeting the educational classification criteria were included in the study.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a structured, close-ended questionnaire designed to measure perceived financial well-being. The instrument assessed four core dimensions: daily financial control, ability to absorb financial shocks, tracking and achieving financial goals, and financial freedom. Responses were rated on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from *Not at All* to *Completely*. The questionnaire was pilot-tested among 20 local workers in Panglao to establish reliability. Internal consistency analysis using Cronbach's alpha yielded an overall coefficient of 0.9226, indicating excellent reliability. Following pilot testing, the finalized instrument was administered to the study participants.

Research Procedure

Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was obtained from relevant local authorities and establishment representatives in Panglao, Bohol. Data were gathered using both paper-based questionnaires and online forms. Participants were informed of the study's purpose and provided consent before completing the survey. Stratified purposive sampling was employed to recruit eligible respondents from identified economic sectors, with assistance from local and barangay officials. Participation was voluntary, and respondents who met the inclusion criteria were included in the final sample.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including frequency distribution and simple percentages, were used to present the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, marital status, monthly income, number of dependents, and job position. Respondents were also categorized based on their educational attainment (college graduates vs. non-college graduates) and their perceived financial well-being, which was assessed using the Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB) Financial Well-Being Scale. Inferential statistical techniques were then employed to examine significant relationships and differences among the identified categories.

In determining the perceived financial well-being of the local workforce in terms of their demographic profile, the weighted mean was computed.

The computed weighted mean results were interpreted using the rating scale.

Table 1. Interpretation of Weighted Mean Ranges

Range	Interpretation
3.21 - 4.00	Completely
2.41 - 3.20	Very well
1.61 - 2.40	Somewhat
0.81 - 1.60	Very Little
0.00 - 0.80	Not at all

The researcher first utilized the CFPB scoring system and worksheet, assigning scores based on the respondent's answers. A positive statement received a score of 4 for "Completely," 3 for "Very Well," 2 for "Somewhat," 1 for "Very Little," and 0 for "Not at all." Conversely, a negative statement had its scoring reversed (0 for "Completely," 1 for "Very Well," 2 for "Somewhat," 3 for "Very Little," and 4 for "Not at all"). This scoring methodology allowed for a quantitative assessment of the responses, facilitating statistical analysis in the research.

Table 2. CFPB Financial Well-being Scores

Total Value	Questionnaire Self-administered		Questionnaire administered by someone else	
	18-61	62+	18-61	62+
0	14	14	16	18
1	19	20	21	23
2	22	24	24	26
3	25	26	27	28
4	27	29	29	30
5	29	31	31	32
6	31	33	33	33
7	32	35	34	35
8	34	36	36	36
9	35	38	38	38
10	37	39	39	39
11	38	41	40	40
12	40	42	42	41

13	41	44	43	43
14	42	45	44	44
15	44	46	45	45
16	45	48	47	46
17	46	49	48	47
18	47	50	49	48
19	49	52	50	49
20	50	53	52	50
21	51	54	53	52
22	52	56	54	53
23	54	57	55	54
24	55	58	57	55
25	56	60	58	56
26	58	61	59	57
27	59	63	60	58
28	60	64	62	60
29	62	66	63	61
30	63	67	65	62
31	65	69	66	64
32	66	71	68	65
33	68	73	70	67
34	69	75	71	68
35	71	77	73	70
36	73	79	76	72
37	75	82	78	75
38	78	84	81	77
39	81	88	85	81
40	86	95	91	87

After obtaining the overall score, the researchers used the interpretation below. The same interpretations were used for both individual and overall interpretations of the results.

Table 3. CFPB Financial Well-being Interpretation

Range	Interpretation
68 – 100	Very High
58 – 67	High
50 – 57	Medium High
38 – 49	Medium Low
30 – 37	Low
0 – 29	Very Low

In determining the significant difference between the financial well-being of the local workforce in terms of their demographic profile, the researchers used the T-test and ANOVA.

RESULTS

Table 4. The Demographic Profile of the Research Participants

	Items	College		Non-College	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Age	18 - 24 years old	61	31.44	53	27.32
	25 - 34 years old	92	47.42	92	47.42
	35 - 44 years old	34	17.53	36	18.56
	45 - 54 years old	7	3.61	13	6.70
	55 - 64 years old	0	0	0	0
	65 and over	0	0	0	0
Marital Status	Single	124	63.92	121	62.37
	Married	70	36.08	73	37.63
Monthly Income	Below ₱10,000	64	32.99	88	45.36
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	114	58.76	89	45.88
	₱20,001 and above	16	8.25	17	8.76
Number of Dependents	0 - 4 dependents	149	76.80	147	75.77
	5 - 10 dependents	29	14.95	40	20.62
	more than 10 dependents	16	8.25	7	3.61
Job Position	Entry-Level / Staff	133	68.56	163	84.02
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	45	23.20	20	10.31
	Managerial / Executive	16	8.25	11	5.67

Table 4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents by educational attainment. The sample in both college and non-college groups is predominantly composed of younger adults, with most respondents falling within the 25–34 age group, followed by those aged 18–24, indicating that the study largely reflects the perspectives of individuals in the early stages of their careers. Consistent with this age distribution, the majority of respondents in both groups are single. In terms of income, most respondents belong to the lower to middle income brackets, particularly those earning ₱10,001–₱20,000, while only a small proportion report higher income levels. Most participants also report having few or no dependents, suggesting relatively limited household financial responsibilities. Regarding job position, respondents in both groups are primarily employed in entry-level or staff roles, with college graduates more frequently represented in supervisory or mid-level positions than non-college graduates. Overall, the demographic profile indicates a workforce characterized by youth, early career status, and modest income levels.

Table 5 shows that both college and non-college graduate respondents perceive themselves as demonstrating very well in their daily financial control. The college graduate local workforce completely pays their electric and water bills, demonstrates very well performance in affording healthy food, prioritizing needs over wants, and demonstrating control over their spending. College graduate respondents also show very well engagement in covering basic expenses and having money left after paying bills;

however, they report only a somewhat level of ability to avoid significant stress or worry about finances.

Table 5. Financial Products and Services Availed by the Respondents

DAILY FINANCIAL CONTROL	College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I can pay my electric bill on time every month.	116	43	22	12	1	3.35	Completely	
I can pay my water bill on time every month.	117	44	17	15	1	3.35	Completely	
I am up to date with my finances.	47	61	62	23	1	2.67	Very Well	
I can afford healthy foods every day.	82	58	41	11	2	3.07	Very Well	
I can consistently afford food that I crave every day.	22	65	68	37	2	2.35	Somewhat	
I have money left over after paying bills and buying.	35	78	51	25	5	2.58	Very Well	
I can cover my basic monthly expenses without borrowing.	55	71	40	19	9	2.74	Very Well	
I spend money thoughtfully and can control my spending.	45	66	53	23	7	2.61	Very Well	
I prioritize my needs over wants when budgeting.	66	83	25	17	3	2.99	Very Well	
I do not experience significant stress or worry related to my finances.	13	56	78	41	6	2.15	Somewhat	
Overall Mean						2.79	Very Well	

DAILY FINANCIAL CONTROL	Non-College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I can pay my electric bill on time every month.	99	50	22	17	6	3.13	Very Well	
I can pay my water bill on time every month.	92	58	19	12	13	3.05	Very Well	

I am up to date with my finances.	46	40	58	32	18	2.33	Somewhat
I can afford healthy foods every day.	44	59	46	35	10	2.47	Very Well
I can consistently afford food that I crave every day.	34	34	61	42	23	2.07	Somewhat
I have money left over after paying bills and buying.	31	38	40	67	18	1.98	Somewhat
I can cover my basic monthly expenses without borrowing.	38	45	44	44	23	2.16	Somewhat
I spend money thoughtfully and can control my spending.	51	47	61	20	15	2.51	Very Well
I prioritize my needs over wants when budgeting.	87	56	27	20	4	3.04	Very Well
I do not experience significant stress or worry related to my finances.	17	35	54	51	37	1.71	Somewhat
Overall Mean						2.45	Very Well

Legend: 4 - Completely 3 - Very Well 2 - Somewhat 1 - Very Little 0 - Not at all

Table 5 shows that both college and non-college graduate respondents exhibit a very well level of daily financial control, as reflected in their overall mean scores. College graduates demonstrate stronger financial control, particularly in paying utility bills on time, affording healthy food, prioritizing needs over wants, and managing spending. However, they report only a somewhat level of ability to avoid financial stress. Similarly, non-college graduates show very well performance in meeting essential financial obligations and prioritizing needs but display somewhat levels of financial control in staying updated with finances, having money left after expenses, covering monthly costs without borrowing, and managing financial stress. Overall, while both groups are able to meet basic financial responsibilities, financial strain and concern remain evident, especially among non-college graduates. These findings are consistent with the study of Xiao and Porto (2017), which found that individuals with higher educational attainment tend to demonstrate stronger financial management behaviors such as timely bill payment and controlled spending, yet may still experience financial stress due to limited financial buffers and income constraints.

Table 6. The Extent of Daily Financial Control Among the Selected Local Workforce in Panglao, Bohol

Extent of Daily Financial Control	College		Non-College	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very High	37	19	20	10
High	100	52	69	36
Medium High	46	24	56	29
Medium Low	11	6	47	24
Low	0	0	2	1
Very Low	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	194	100	194	100

Table 6 presents the extent of daily financial control among college and non-college graduate respondents. The majority of respondents in both groups fall within the *high* and *medium high* levels of daily financial control, indicating generally strong financial management practices. College graduates are more concentrated in the *high* and *very high* categories, with no respondents reporting *low* or *very low* control. In contrast, while most non-college graduates also report *high* levels of financial control, a notable proportion fall under the *medium low* category, and a small number report *low* control. Overall, the findings suggest stronger and more consistent daily financial control among college graduates compared to non-college graduates.

Table 7. Perceived Ability to Absorb Financial Shocks

ABILITY TO ABSORB FINANCIAL SHOCKS	College						
	4	3	2	1	0	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
I have life insurance.	57	37	39	38	23	2.35	Somewhat
I have insurance for my home and belongings.	26	30	57	47	34	1.83	Somewhat
I can handle small, unexpected costs without problems.	64	45	59	22	4	2.74	Very Well
I can manage unexpected expenses without borrowing money.	32	67	64	22	9	2.47	Very Well
I could easily cover unexpected medical bills in my family.	36	45	58	38	17	2.23	Somewhat
I have emergency funds for unexpected costs.	38	42	56	45	13	2.24	Somewhat
I have savings that can cover at least three months of expenses.	32	52	47	45	18	2.18	Somewhat
I have a financial safety net in case of job loss.	40	47	58	31	18	2.31	Somewhat

I have current retirement savings that will support me in the future.	51	48	39	28	28	2.34	Somewhat
Overall Mean						2.35	Somewhat

ABILITY TO ABSORB FINANCIAL SHOCKS	Non-College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I have health insurance.	86	35	28	18	27	2.70	Very Well	
I have life insurance.	59	32	35	27	41	2.21	Somewhat	
I have insurance for my home and belongings.	25	34	29	31	75	1.50	Very Little	
I can handle small, unexpected costs without problems.	40	54	47	31	22	2.30	Somewhat	
I can manage unexpected expenses without borrowing money.	32	40	44	45	33	1.96	Somewhat	
I could easily cover unexpected medical bills in my family.	17	34	57	55	31	1.75	Somewhat	
I have emergency funds for unexpected costs.	26	24	47	61	36	1.71	Somewhat	
I have savings that can cover at least three months of expenses.	21	29	48	59	37	1.68	Somewhat	
I have a financial safety net in case of job loss.	32	37	38	58	29	1.92	Somewhat	
I have current retirement savings that will support me in the future.	31	34	46	34	49	1.81	Somewhat	
Overall Mean						1.95	Somewhat	

Legend: 4 - Completely 3 - Very Well 2 - Somewhat 1 - Very Little 0 - Not at all

Table 7 presents the perceived ability of the respondents to absorb financial shocks. Both college and non-college graduate respondents demonstrate an overall *somewhat* level of ability to absorb financial shocks, with college graduates exhibiting slightly higher mean scores than non-college graduates. Among college graduates, *very well* ratings are observed in health insurance coverage, handling small unexpected costs, and managing unexpected expenses without borrowing. However, most indicators—such as life insurance, emergency funds, savings for extended expenses, financial safety nets for job loss, and retirement savings—are rated *somewhat*, with home and belongings insurance emerging as a weaker area. Similarly, non-college graduates report *very well* performance only in health insurance coverage, while most other indicators are rated *somewhat*. Notably, home and belongings insurance among non-college graduates is rated *very little*, indicating limited protection against property-related financial shocks.

Table 8. The Extent of Ability to Absorb Financial Shocks Among the Selected Local Workforce in Panglao

Extent of Ability to Absorb Financial Shocks	College		Non-College	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very High	28	14	8	4
High	46	24	33	17
Medium High	62	32	61	32
Medium Low	43	22	65	34
Low	12	6	21	11
Very Low	3	2	6	3
TOTAL	194	100	194	100

Table 8 shows that most college graduate respondents fall within the medium-high category in terms of their ability to absorb financial shocks, with the other respondents distributed across the high and medium-low levels and only a small proportion in the low and very low categories. This suggests that college graduates generally possess a moderate level of financial resilience and are better prepared to handle unexpected expenses. In contrast, the non-college graduate respondents mostly fall within the medium-low category, with relatively higher proportions in the lower ranges and fewer reaching the high levels, indicating weaker financial shock absorption than college graduates. These findings are supported by the theoretical perspectives of Lusardi and Mitchell (2014), who emphasize that financial literacy and planning—particularly the presence of emergency savings—significantly enhance an individual’s ability to withstand financial shocks. Similarly, the FINRA Investor Education Foundation highlights that individuals with lower financial preparedness often rely on short-term and unsustainable coping strategies during financial emergencies. Together, these theoretical insights help explain the observed differences in financial shock absorption between college and non-college graduate respondents.

Table 9. Perceived Tracking and Achieving Financial Goals

TRACKING AND ACHIEVING FINANCIAL GOALS	College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I check my spending every week to know my balances.	45	54	58	28	9	2.51	Very Well	
I use apps to budget and track my money, which helps me manage it well.	49	48	42	21	34	2.29	Somewhat	
I have a system for tracking my financial progress.	68	47	46	22	11	2.72	Very Well	
I can pay off my debts because I monitor my income and expenses.	65	45	61	22	1	2.78	Very Well	
I always pay off my credit cards or loans to avoid paying extra in interest.	78	49	31	19	17	2.78	Very Well	

I had managed to pay down my debt this year making my interest payments lower.	46	79	32	20	17	2.60	Very Well
I regularly save money every month for my summer or December travels.	30	44	64	39	17	2.16	Somewhat
I'm consistently hitting my monthly savings goals.	26	53	59	41	15	2.18	Somewhat
I've cut back on eating out and entertainment to reach my savings goals.	45	50	66	21	12	2.49	Very Well
I can achieve my dreams because I track and manage my money well.	73	44	56	19	2	2.86	Very Well
Overall Mean						2.54	Very Well

TRACKING AND ACHIEVING FINANCIAL GOALS	Non-College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I check my spending every week to know my balances.	28	56	54	33	23	2.17	Somewhat	
I use apps to budget and track my money, which helps me manage it well.	28	49	28	38	51	1.82	Somewhat	
I have a system for tracking my financial progress.	51	48	53	15	27	2.42	Very Well	
I can pay off my debts because I monitor my income and expenses.	52	40	66	24	12	2.49	Very Well	
I always pay off my credit cards or loans to avoid paying extra in interest.	32	41	48	29	44	1.94	Somewhat	
I had managed to pay down my debt this year making my interest payments lower.	36	56	35	40	27	2.18	Somewhat	
I regularly save money every month for my summer or December travels.	21	35	42	53	43	1.68	Somewhat	
I'm consistently hitting my monthly savings goals.	26	32	60	45	31	1.88	Somewhat	
I've cut back on eating out and entertainment to reach my savings goals.	32	52	61	25	24	2.22	Somewhat	
I can achieve my dreams because I track and manage my money well.	52	51	58	20	13	2.56	Very Well	
Overall Mean						2.14	Somewhat	

Table 9 presents the perceived ability of respondents to track and achieve financial goals. College graduate respondents report an overall *very well* level of financial goal tracking and achievement, while non-college graduate respondents report an overall *somewhat* level. College graduates demonstrate stronger performance in monitoring spending, maintaining systems to track financial progress, paying off debts, and managing loans, with several indicators rated *very well*. However, both groups report only *somewhat* levels in regular savings behavior, including consistently meeting monthly savings targets and saving for future expenses. Non-college graduates exhibit lower mean scores across most indicators, particularly in the use of budgeting tools, regular saving, and reducing discretionary spending to meet financial goals. Overall, the findings

indicate clearer and more effective financial goal management among college graduates compared to non-college graduates.

Table 10. The Extent of Tracking and Achieving Financial Goals Among the Selected Local Workforce in Panglao, Bohol

Extent of Tracking and Achieving Financial Goals	College		Non-College	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very High	32	16	13	7
High	71	37	40	21
Medium High	55	28	65	34
Medium Low	34	18	69	36
Low	2	1	5	3
Very Low	0	0	2	1
TOTAL	194	100	194	100

Table 10 presents the extent of tracking and achieving financial goals among college and non-college graduate respondents. Most college graduates fall within the *high* and *medium high* categories, indicating generally strong financial goal tracking and management, with no respondents classified under *very low*. In contrast, non-college graduates are predominantly concentrated in the *medium low* and *medium high* categories, with fewer respondents reaching the *high* level and a small number falling under *low* or *very low*. Overall, the distribution indicates more consistent and advanced financial goal tracking among college graduates compared to non-college graduates.

Table 11. Perceived Financial Freedom

FINANCIAL FREEDOM	College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I have enough money to travel anywhere I want.	45	60	34	27	28	2.35	Somewhat	
I have enough money to pursue any education I choose.	53	51	33	30	27	2.38	Somewhat	
I can make any investment I desire, without worrying about money.	41	51	42	32	28	2.23	Somewhat	
I am able to pay my bills and buy groceries without difficulty.	66	64	48	12	4	2.91	Very Well	
My debt is manageable and I feel capable of repaying it.	83	25	51	35	83	2.91	Very Well	
I have savings and do not live paycheck to paycheck.	69	59	42	20	4	2.87	Very Well	
I can afford my current lifestyle comfortably.	50	48	67	22	7	2.58	Very Well	

I can afford new clothes or shoes for a special occasion like a birthday or holiday.	30	76	61	21	6	2.53	Very Well
I can comfortably support my family's needs.	62	54	51	26	1	2.77	Very Well
I am able to survive without working for long hours.	55	40	55	31	13	2.48	Very Well
Overall Mean						2.60	Very Well

FINANCIAL FREEDOM	Non-College						Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1	0			
I have enough money to travel anywhere I want.	18	41	36	43	56	1.60	Very Little	
I have enough money to pursue any education I choose.	24	35	36	41	58	1.62	Somewhat	
I can make any investment I desire, without worrying about money.	18	45	31	45	55	1.62	Somewhat	
I am able to pay my bills and buy groceries without difficulty.	58	47	33	33	23	2.43	Very Well	
My debt is manageable and I feel capable of repaying it.	64	55	45	25	5	2.76	Very Well	
I have savings and do not live paycheck to paycheck.	63	44	48	22	17	2.59	Very Well	
I can afford my current lifestyle comfortably.	38	37	44	48	27	2.06	Somewhat	
I can afford new clothes or shoes for a special occasion like a birthday or holiday.	22	41	61	51	19	1.98	Somewhat	
I can comfortably support my family's needs.	44	37	66	30	17	2.31	Somewhat	
I am able to survive without working for long hours.	54	28	34	40	38	2.10	Somewhat	
Overall Mean						2.11	Somewhat	

Table 11 presents the perceived level of financial freedom among college and non-college graduate respondents. College graduates demonstrate an overall *very well* level of financial freedom, particularly in meeting essential needs such as paying bills, managing debt, maintaining savings, supporting family needs, and sustaining daily living without excessive work hours. However, indicators related to discretionary and opportunity-based choices—such as traveling freely, pursuing further education, and making investments without financial concern—are rated only *somewhat*. In contrast, non-college graduates report an overall *somewhat* level of financial freedom. While they show *very well* performance in meeting basic necessities, most lifestyle- and opportunity-related indicators remain at the *somewhat* or *very little* levels, particularly in the ability to

travel freely. Overall, the results indicate a higher and more comprehensive level of financial freedom among college graduates compared to non-college graduates.

Table 12. The Extent of Financial Freedom Among the Selected Local Workforce in Panglao, Bohol

Extent of Financial Freedom	College		Non-College	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very High	36	19	19	10
High	67	35	34	18
Medium High	59	30	60	31
Medium Low	28	14	69	36
Low	4	2	11	6
Very Low	0	0	1	0.05
TOTAL	194	100	194	100

Table 12 presents the extent of perceived financial freedom among college and non-college graduate respondents. College graduates are predominantly concentrated in the *high* and *very high* categories, indicating a stronger level of financial freedom. In contrast, non-college graduates are mainly distributed across the *medium high* and *medium low* categories, with a higher proportion appearing in the lower levels compared to college graduates. Only a small number of respondents in either group fall under the *low* or *very low* categories. Overall, the distribution suggests that college graduates experience a higher extent of financial freedom than non-college graduates.

Table 13. The Extent of Financial Well-Being Among the Selected Local Workforce in Panglao, Bohol

Extent of Financial Well-being	College		Non-College	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very High	33	17	10	5
High	71	37	34	18
Medium High	62	32	74	38
Medium Low	26	13	74	38
Low	2	1	2	1
Very Low	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	194	100	194	100

Table 13 presents the extent of overall financial well-being among college and non-college graduate respondents. College graduates are predominantly concentrated in the *high* and *very high* categories, indicating a stronger overall level of financial well-being. In contrast, non-college graduates are mainly distributed across the *medium high* and *medium low* categories, with fewer respondents reaching the *high* or *very high* levels. Only a small proportion of respondents in both groups fall under the *low* category, and none are classified as *very low*.

Table 14. Significant Difference in the Perceived Financial Well-being of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Variables	Age	N	\bar{x}	College		
				P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	18 - 24 years old	61	4.89	0.088	Not significant	Accept Ho ^a
	25 - 34 years old	92	4.73			
	35 - 44 years old	34	5.12			
	45 - 54 years old	7	4.57			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	18 - 24 years old	61	4.23	0.020	Significant	Reject Ho ^b
	25 - 34 years old	92	3.88			
	35 - 44 years old	34	4.68			
	45 - 54 years old	7	4.00			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	18 - 24 years old	61	4.67	0.176	Not significant	Accept Ho ^c
	25 - 34 years old	92	4.37			
	35 - 44 years old	34	4.62			
	45 - 54 years old	7	4.14			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Financial freedom	18 - 24 years old	61	4.72	0.022	Significant	Reject Ho ^d
	25 - 34 years old	92	4.38			
	35 - 44 years old	34	4.74			
	45 - 54 years old	7	3.86			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Financial Well-being	18-24 years old	61	4.69	0.052	Not Significant	Accept Ho ^e
	25-34 years old	92	4.38			
	35-44 years old	34	3.85			
	45-54 years old	7	4.14			
	55-64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and above	0	0.00			
Non- College						
Variables	Age	N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	18 - 24 years old	53	4.19	0.455	Not significant	Accept Ho ^a
	25 - 34 years old	92	4.27			
	35 - 44 years old	36	4.36			
	45 - 54 years old	13	4.77			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	18 - 24 years old	53	3.49	0.257	Not significant	Accept Ho ^b
	25 - 34 years old	92	3.62			
	35 - 44 years old	36	3.58			
	45 - 54 years old	13	4.08			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	18 - 24 years old	53	3.89	0.332	Not significant	Accept Ho ^c
	25 - 34 years old	92	3.97			
	35 - 44 years old	36	3.67			
	45 - 54 years old	13	4.15			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Financial freedom	18 - 24 years old	53	3.81	0.237	Not significant	Accept Ho ^d
	25 - 34 years old	92	3.86			
	35 - 44 years old	36	3.89			
	45 - 54 years old	13	4.38			
	55 - 64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and over	0	0.00			
Financial Well-being	18-24 years old	53	3.79	0.300	Not Significant	Accept Ho ^e
	25-34 years old	92	3.88			
	35-44 years old	36	3.83			
	45-54 years old	13	4.31			
	55-64 years old	0	0.00			
	65 and above	0	0.00			

Table 14 presents the significant differences in perceived financial well-being across age groups among college and non-college graduate respondents. Among college graduates, age does not significantly differentiate overall financial well-being. However, significant differences are observed in two specific dimensions—*ability to absorb financial shocks* and *financial freedom*—indicating that these aspects vary across age groups. No significant differences are found in daily financial control or tracking and achieving financial goals among college graduates. In contrast, non-college graduate respondents show no significant differences across all four dimensions of financial well-being when grouped according to age. Overall, the results indicate that age-related differences are limited and dimension-specific among college graduates, while financial well-being among non-college graduates remains statistically consistent across age groups.

Table 15. Significant Difference in the Perceived Financial Well-being of the Respondents in Terms of Marital Status

		College				
Variables	Marital Status	N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	Single	124	4.73	0.017	Significant	Reject Ho ^{3a}
	Married	70	5.03			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	Single	124	3.82	0.001	Significant	Reject Ho ^{3b}
	Married	70	4.69			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	Single	124	4.40	0.048	Significant	Reject Ho ^{3c}
	Married	70	4.69			
Financial freedom	Single	124	4.38	0.005	Significant	Reject Ho ^{3d}
	Married	70	4.80			
Financial Well-being	Single	124	4.39	0.002	Significant	Reject Ho ³
	Married	70	4.84			
		Non-College				
Variables	Marital Status	N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	Single	121	4.26	0.545	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{4a}
	Married	73	4.36			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	Single	121	3.51	0.130	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{4b}
	Married	73	3.77			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	Single	121	3.85	0.386	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{4c}
	Married	73	3.99			
Financial freedom	Single	121	3.84	0.488	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{4d}
	Married	73	3.96			
Financial Well-being	Single	121	3.82	0.261	Not significant	Accept Ho⁴
	Married	73	3.97			

Table 15 presents the significant differences in perceived financial well-being when respondents are grouped according to marital status. Among college graduates, marital

status significantly differentiates all four dimensions of financial well-being—daily financial control, ability to absorb financial shocks, tracking and achieving financial goals, and financial freedom—as well as overall financial well-being. Married college graduates consistently report higher mean scores than single respondents across all dimensions. In contrast, no significant differences are observed among non-college graduate respondents across any dimension of financial well-being when grouped by marital status. Overall, the results indicate that marital status is a significant factor in shaping perceived financial well-being among college graduates but not among non-college graduates.

Table 16. Significant Difference in the Perceived Financial Well-being of the Respondents in Terms of Monthly Income

Variables	Age	College				
		N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	Below ₱10,000	64	4.86	0.599	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{5a}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	114	4.85			
	₱20,001 and above	16	4.69			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	Below ₱10,000	64	4.34	0.198	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{5b}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	114	4.01			
	₱20,001 and above	16	4.19			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	Below ₱10,000	64	4.73	0.017	Significant	Reject Ho ^{5c}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	114	4.43			
	₱20,001 and above	16	4.06			
Financial freedom	Below ₱10,000	64	4.66	0.445	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{5d}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	114	4.46			
	₱20,001 and above	16	4.56			
Financial Well-being	Below ₱10,000	64	4.75	0.102	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{5e}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	114	4.46			
	₱20,001 and above	16	4.38			

Variables	Age	Non-College				
		N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	Below ₱10,000	88	4.02	0.002	Significant	Reject Ho ^{6a}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	89	4.48			
	₱20,001 and above	17	4.76			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	Below ₱10,000	88	3.41	0.003	Significant	Reject Ho ^{6b}
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	89	3.64			
	₱20,001 and above	17	4.47			
	Below ₱10,000	88	3.72	0.001	Significant	

Tracking and achieving financial goals	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	89	3.92			Reject Ho ^c
	₱20,001 and above	17	4.76			
Financial freedom	Below ₱10,000	88	3.76	0.172	Not significant	Accept Ho ^d
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	89	3.92			
	₱20,001 and above	17	4.35			
Financial Well-being	Below ₱10,000	88	3.66	0.002	Significant	Reject Ho^e
	₱10,001 - ₱20,000	89	3.97			
	₱20,001 and above	17	4.53			

Table 16 presents the significant differences in perceived financial well-being when respondents are grouped according to monthly income. Among college graduates, monthly income does not significantly differentiate daily financial control, ability to absorb financial shocks, financial freedom, or overall financial well-being. A significant difference is observed only in the dimension of tracking and achieving financial goals. In contrast, non-college graduate respondents show significant differences across most dimensions, including daily financial control, ability to absorb financial shocks, tracking and achieving financial goals, and overall financial well-being, while no significant difference is observed in financial freedom. Overall, the results indicate that monthly income plays a limited role in differentiating financial well-being among college graduates but exerts a stronger influence among non-college graduates. These findings align with the study of Netemeyer et al. (2018), which found that income has a stronger impact on perceived financial well-being among individuals with lower levels of education, as they are more vulnerable to income fluctuations and have fewer financial resources to buffer financial shocks, whereas individuals with higher educational attainment tend to rely more on financial planning and goal-setting behaviors than income level alone.

Table 17. Significant Difference in the Perceived Financial Well-being of the Respondents in Terms of Number of Dependents

Variables	Age	College				
		N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	0 - 4 dependents	149	4.84	0.030	Significant	Reject Ho ^{7a}
	5 - 10 dependents	29	5.03			
	more than 10 dependents	16	4.50			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	0 - 4 dependents	149	4.01	0.017	Significant	Reject Ho ^{7b}
	5 - 10 dependents	29	4.55			
	more than 10 dependents	16	4.50			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	0 - 4 dependents	149	4.44	0.340	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{7c}
	5 - 10 dependents	29	4.76			
	more than 10 dependents	16	4.56			
Financial freedom	0 - 4 dependents	149	4.49	0.190	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{7d}
	5 - 10 dependents	29	4.83			
	more than 10 dependents	16	4.38			
Financial Well-being	0 - 4 dependents	149	4.52	0.322	Not significant	Accept Ho ⁷
	5 - 10 dependents	29	4.79			
	more than 10 dependents	16	4.44			

Variables	Age	Non-College				
		N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	0 - 4 dependents	147	4.29	0.775	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{8a}
	5 - 10 dependents	40	4.38			
	more than 10 dependents	7	4.14			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	0 - 4 dependents	147	3.53	0.003	Significant	Reject Ho ^{8b}
	5 - 10 dependents	40	3.75			
	more than 10 dependents	7	4.43			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	0 - 4 dependents	147	3.85	0.290	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{8c}
	5 - 10 dependents	40	4.00			
	more than 10 dependents	7	4.43			
Financial freedom	0 - 4 dependents	147	3.83	0.169	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{8d}
	5 - 10 dependents	40	4.00			
	more than 10 dependents	7	4.43			
Financial Well-being	0 - 4 dependents	147	3.82	0.039	Significant	Reject Ho⁸
	5 - 10 dependents	40	3.98			
	more than 10 dependents	7	4.43			

Table 17 presents the significant differences in perceived financial well-being when respondents are grouped according to the number of dependents. Among college graduates, significant differences are observed in *daily financial control* and *ability to absorb financial shocks*, while no significant differences are found in *tracking and achieving financial goals*, *financial freedom*, or overall *financial well-being*. In contrast, among non-college graduates, the number of dependents significantly differentiates the *ability to absorb financial shocks* and overall *financial well-being*, while no significant differences are observed in *daily financial control*, *tracking and achieving financial goals*, or *financial freedom*. Overall, the results indicate that the influence of dependents on financial well-being is dimension-specific and differs between college and non-college graduate respondents.

Table 18. Significant Difference in the Perceived Financial Well-being of the Respondents in Terms of Job Positions

Variables	Age	College				
		N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	Entry-Level / Staff	133	4.77	0.088	Not Significant	Accept Ho ^{9a}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	45	5.09			
	Managerial / Executive	16	4.69			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	Entry-Level / Staff	133	3.95	0.010	Significant	Reject Ho ^{9b}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	45	4.64			
	Managerial / Executive	16	4.25			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	Entry-Level / Staff	133	4.49	0.347	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{9c}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	45	4.62			
	Managerial / Executive	16	4.25			
Financial freedom	Entry-Level / Staff	133	4.44	0.072	Not significant	Accept Ho ^{9d}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	45	4.87			
	Managerial / Executive	16	4.38			
Financial Well-being	Entry-Level/Staff	133	4.50	0.108	Not Significant	Accept Ho ⁹
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	45	4.80			
	Managerial / Executive	16	4.31			

Variables	Age	Non- College				
		N	\bar{x}	P	Interpretation	Decision
Daily Financial Control	Entry-Level / Staff	163	4.19	0.009	Significant	Reject Ho ^{10a}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	20	4.90			
	Managerial / Executive	11	4.82			
Ability to absorb financial shocks	Entry-Level / Staff	Ho ^{9a}	3.47	0.006	Significant	Reject Ho ^{10b}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	20	4.30			
	Managerial / Executive	11	4.36			
Tracking and achieving financial goals	Entry-Level / Staff	163	3.78	0.005	Significant	Reject Ho ^{10c}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	20	4.65			
	Managerial / Executive	11	4.36			
Financial freedom	Entry-Level / Staff	163	3.80	0.079	Not Significant	Accept Ho ^{10d}
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	20	4.50			
	Managerial / Executive	11	4.09			
Financial Well-being	Entry-Level/Staff	163	3.75	0.006	Significant	Reject Ho ¹⁰
	Supervisory / Mid-Level	20	4.65			
	Managerial / Executive	11	4.36			

Table 18 presents the significant differences in perceived financial well-being when respondents are grouped according to job position. Among college graduates, job position does not significantly differentiate overall financial well-being. A significant difference is observed only in the dimension of *ability to absorb financial shocks*, while *daily financial control*, *tracking and achieving financial goals*, and *financial freedom* do not vary significantly across job positions.

In contrast, among non-college graduate respondents, job position significantly differentiates *daily financial control*, *ability to absorb financial shocks*, *tracking and achieving financial goals*, and overall *financial well-being*. No significant difference is observed in *financial freedom*. Across these significant dimensions, supervisory or mid-level respondents consistently report higher mean scores than entry-level/staff and managerial/executive respondents. Overall, the results indicate that job position plays a more substantial role in shaping financial well-being among non-college graduates than among college graduates.

DISCUSSION

This study sought to examine the financial well-being of the college and non-college local workforce in Panglao, Bohol.

The researchers utilized a descriptive research design and a comparative research design to achieve the purpose of the study. Data were gathered through survey questionnaires to obtain the necessary information from the respondents. Furthermore, stratified purposive sampling was employed to ensure balanced representation between college and non-college graduate respondents, allowing for a more accurate comparison of their perceived financial well-being.

Findings

The following findings are presented based on the interpretation and analysis of the data collected:

1. The demographic profile of the respondents shows that the majority of both groups, college and non-college local workforce are young adults, primarily within the 25–34 age range. Most respondents are single and earn a monthly income between ₱10,001 and ₱20,000. The majority have 0–4 dependents, and the workforce is largely composed of entry-level or staff employees.
2. The study aimed to measure the extent to which the respondents employed the elements of financial well-being. The following have been established:
 - 2.1 The findings show that both college and non-college graduate respondents perceive their overall daily financial control as very well, reflecting a generally positive self-assessment of their ability to manage daily financial

responsibilities. Most respondents in the college graduate category demonstrate high daily financial control, with a significant number reaching very high and medium high levels. Similarly, most non-college graduate respondents fall within the high range, with notable portions also achieving very high and medium high levels.

2.2 In terms of ability to absorb financial shocks, both college and non-college local workforce perceive their ability to absorb financial shocks as somewhat, indicating a shared moderate level of resilience against unexpected expenses. Most respondents in the college graduate demonstrate medium-high in their ability to absorb financial shocks, followed by high, medium-low, and very high. In contrast, non-college graduates primarily falls within the medium-low extent with substantial portions achieving medium-high to high.

2.3 In terms of tracking and achieving financial goals, college graduates perceived their tracking and achievement of goals as very well, while non-college graduates respondents assessed themselves at a somewhat level. Most college graduates demonstrate a high extent of tracking and goal management with a considerable amount of medium-high and medium-low. Conversely, non-college graduate respondents are generally at a medium-low extent with substantial portions in medium-high to high.

2.4 When it comes to financial freedom, college graduates report a perception of very well, whereas non-college graduate respondents perceive it as somewhat. The extent of this freedom is high for most of the college graduates followed by medium-high to high. For the non-college local workforce, the extent is more concentrated in the medium-low range with considerable portions achieving medium-high to high.

3. The study aimed to measure the extent of financial well-being among the selected local workforce, and the findings reveal a noticeable difference between college and non-college graduate respondents. Most college graduate respondents exhibit a generally high extent of financial well-being, with a large proportion falling within the high and medium-high levels. Likewise, most non-college graduate respondents are concentrated in the medium-high and medium-low levels of financial well-being, with only a few respondents demonstrating a high or very high extent.

4. The study aimed to determine if there is a significant difference in the perceived financial well-being of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile. The following have been established:

The findings indicate that only marital status shows a significant difference in overall financial well-being among college graduate respondents, while no significant differences are observed in age, monthly income, number of dependents, and job position. This

suggests that college graduates tend to maintain a relatively stable level of financial well-being regardless of these demographic and occupational characteristics.

In contrast, non-college graduate respondents exhibit clear and significant differences across monthly income, number of dependents, and job position, while no significant differences are found in age and marital status. These findings suggest that the financial well-being of non-college graduate respondents is more affected by their income, household responsibilities, and occupational rank than by other demographic factors.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the perceived financial well-being of the local workforce in Panglao, Bohol varies according to educational attainment. A majority of college graduates report a higher extent of financial well-being, largely falling within the high and medium-high categories, whereas a majority of non-college graduates are concentrated in the medium-high and medium-low levels. While both groups generally view their financial situation positively, college graduates demonstrate a stronger sense of financial security and stability. Across the local workforce, daily financial control emerges as the strongest element of financial well-being, reflecting confidence in managing routine financial responsibilities, while the ability to absorb financial shocks remains comparatively weaker, indicating vulnerability to unexpected financial demands. Overall, these findings highlight the important role of education in shaping financial resilience, with college graduates exhibiting more consistent and stable perceptions of financial well-being than their non-college counterparts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the financial well-being of the respondents:

1. For Local Government Unit (LGU) and Policymakers

Local government units should strengthen economic safety nets through community-based credit cooperatives, micro-insurance, and emergency savings programs to address the workforce's limited ability to absorb financial shocks. Given that college graduates demonstrate relatively stable financial well-being even at lower income levels, LGU-led initiatives should promote budgeting and financial management across all income groups. At the same time, since the financial well-being of non-college graduates is more strongly income-dependent, policymakers should advocate for living wages, income stability, and job security measures, including fair wage structures and cost-of-living adjustments, to improve financial well-being across the labor force.

2. For Employers and Private Organizations

They are encouraged to implement inclusive financial wellness programs that respond to employees' varying needs. For non-college graduate workers,

initiatives should prioritize emergency fund building, debt management, and income stability, while programs for college graduates should emphasize long-term financial planning, such as savings growth, wealth diversification, and retirement preparedness. Integrating financial literacy into professional development is essential, as financial capability functions not only as a life skill but also as a productivity-enhancing tool that reduces financial stress and improves employee morale. Employers should also provide clear career pathways toward higher ranks such as supervisory or mid-level positions, which are associated with higher perceived financial well being.

3. For the Local Workforce

They are encouraged to actively participate in financial education opportunities, mentorship programs, and workplace wellness initiatives. Early-career, lower-income, and non-college graduate workers may particularly benefit from mentorship that facilitates the sharing of practical budgeting strategies and financial coping mechanisms from more experienced colleagues. By strengthening budgeting habits, goal-tracking practices, and adaptive financial behaviors, workers can enhance daily financial control and resilience, while pursuing strategic career advancement that supports long-term financial stability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the appropriate institutional review body prior to data collection. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was secured from all respondents before survey administration. Eligible participants were adults (18 years and above) who had resided and worked in Panglao, Bohol, for at least three years and met the study's inclusion criteria. Respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, and no personally identifiable information was collected. All data were used solely for research purposes and handled in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). The researchers declared no conflict of interest, and no incentives or compensation were provided to participants.

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